

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Diversity and seasonal dynamics of the marine diatom family Chaetocerotaceae (Bacillariophyta, Mediophyceae) in Catalan coastal waters (northwest Mediterranean)

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Abstract

The family Chaetocerotaceae includes the genera *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrium*, with *Chaetoceros* being one of the most cosmopolitan, abundant, and diverse diatom genera in the oceans. This study investigated the diversity and seasonal dynamics of the Chaetocerotaceae in surface waters of two coastal sites along the Catalan coast (Barcelona and Blanes Bay), from 2004 to 2019. A combination of field sample observations, morphological (light and scanning electron microscopy), and molecular (SSU and LSU rDNA gene sequences) analyses of monoclonal cultures, and V4 18S rDNA metabarcoding time-series data from Blanes was used for species identification. The seasonal dynamics of both genera were investigated during two annual cycles at both sites through monthly light microscopy observations and, at Blanes Bay, also through the metabarcoding dataset. A total of 60 species of *Chaetoceros* and 10 of *Bacteriastrium* were detected. Based on cell ultramorphology and SSU and LSU rDNA gene phylogenies, two species within the genus *Chaetoceros* are putatively new to science, although they are not formally described here. The most abundant and frequent taxa were *C. tenuissimus*, *C. socialis*, *C. vixvisibilis*, and the *C. curvisetus* complex. These species presented similar seasonal trends at both sites, with *C. tenuissimus* and *C. vixvisibilis* peaking in late spring and summer, whereas *C. socialis* was more prevalent in winter. The *C. curvisetus* complex did not show a clear seasonality although its components were less abundant in summer. These results highlight the value of integrating morphological and molecular approaches to assess the diversity and ecological dynamics of the dominant *Chaetoceros* species.

KEYWORDS

Bacteriastrium, *Chaetoceros*, metabarcoding, morphology, phylogeny, rDNA, taxonomy

Abbreviations: ASV, amplicon sequence variant; CFA, continuous flow analysis; CTD, conductivity temperature depth; dNTPs, deoxynucleotide triphosphate; LM, light microscopy; LSU, large subunit; PA/AA, pervalvar/apical ratio; PCR, polymerase chain reaction; RDA, redundancy analysis; SEM, scanning electron microscopy; SSU, small subunit.

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INTRODUCTION

Chaetocerotaceae is one of the most important marine diatom families in terms of diversity and abundance worldwide. Members of this family play significant roles in the global carbon and silica cycles and constitute an important fraction of the marine primary producers. Chaetocerotaceae comprises the genera *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrium*, characterized by the presence of valves with long setae and the capacity to form chains, usually by the fusion of sibling setae. Generally, *Chaetoceros* has two setae per valve, each emerging from the opposite margin, whereas *Bacteriastrium* setae range from six to 20 per valve, arranged radially. The genus *Chaetoceros* has been especially abundant in nutrient-rich and highly hydrodynamic environments such as coastal areas and upwelling zones (Tilstone et al., 2000; Zhang et al., 2025) and often produces significant blooms. Some species, either through setae or mucilage production, can cause physiological damage or even mortality of fish (Horner et al., 1997; Treasurer et al., 2003). *Bacteriastrium* species are usually present in low numbers and rarely form blooms.

Currently, there are more than 250 accepted species names for *Chaetoceros* and 15 for *Bacteriastrium* (Guiry & Guiry, 2025). The introduction of DNA sequence analysis in systematics has allowed the discovery of new species and revealed a cryptic diversity impossible to detect with classical morphology-based methods. Furthermore, molecular metabarcoding surveys are an emerging approach for revealing environmental diversity, allowing the tracing of the seasonal succession and the spatial distribution of species and communities (Cui et al., 2023; Gaonkar et al., 2020).

The incorporation of molecular techniques has improved our understanding of the phylogeny and classification of the Chaetocerotaceae family. Currently, the traditional classification (based on morphological features of the organisms) of *Chaetoceros* into three subgenera (*Phaeoceros*, *Hyalochaete*, and *Bacteriastroidea*) and several sections and of *Bacteriastrium* into two sections (*Sagitatta* and *Isomorpha*) is unsupported. The newest classification of this family, based on a multi-genic (nuclear, plastid, and mitochondrial) phylogeny, recognizes only the subdivision of *Chaetoceros* into several sections (De Luca, Sarno, et al., 2019).

In the Mediterranean Sea, organisms of the genus *Chaetoceros* constitute an important fraction of the diatom community (Siokou-Frangou et al., 2010). High abundances of *Chaetoceros* have been reported mainly in coastal areas (Arin et al., 2013; Bosak et al., 2016; Margalef, 1969; Ribera d'Alcalà et al., 2004), fronts and gyres (Arin et al., 2002; Estrada, 1991; Fiala et al., 1994), deep convection zones (Estrada et al., 2014), and deep-chlorophyll maxima (Gotsis-Skretas et al., 1999; Latasa et al., 2017). A high diversity of species of this genus has already been detected in Mediterranean waters

through morphological identification by classical microscopy (Bosak & Sarno, 2017; Margalef, 1957; Margalef et al., 1959; Marino & Modigh, 1981; Viličić et al., 2002), but the recent incorporation of molecular techniques has allowed the detection of additional species (Gaonkar et al., 2018, 2020), many of them new to science (Arin et al., 2022; Gaonkar et al., 2018). *Bacteriastrium* is not as abundant as *Chaetoceros* in Mediterranean waters, but it is represented by most of the small number of species described for this genus (Bosak et al., 2016; Gaonkar et al., 2020; Margalef, 1957; Margalef et al., 1959). Despite the importance of the Chaetocerotaceae family, information on the seasonal dynamics of the main *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrium* species and their ecological preferences in Mediterranean waters is scarce (Bosak et al., 2016; Gaonkar et al., 2020).

In the present study, we combined morphological and molecular approaches to explore the diversity and the seasonal dynamics of the Chaetocerotaceae family in surface waters of the Catalan coast (northwest Mediterranean). To uncover the maximum possible species diversity, we observed field samples, established monoclonal cultures that were subsequently subjected to morphological and molecular characterization, and explored a V4 18S rDNA metabarcoding time-series dataset from the Blanes Bay Microbial Observatory (Giner et al., 2019; <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB23788>). The seasonal dynamics of *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrium* species were assessed based on this latter dataset in combination with light microscopy observations during two annual cycles at the same coastal site and at the Barcelona Coastal Oceanographic Observatory. The environmental parameters that have driven the succession patterns of the main *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrium* species have also been discussed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sampling strategy and environmental determinations

Sampling was carried out in two long-standing and well-studied stations located on the Catalan coast (northwest Mediterranean): the Blanes Bay Microbial Observatory (41°40' N, 2°48' E) and the Barcelona Coastal Oceanographic Observatory (Station 1.4; 41°23' N, 2°13' E), hereafter Blanes and Barcelona. Detailed information about these sites is in Gasol et al. (2016) and Arin et al. (2013), respectively. Since 2001 (Blanes) and 2002 (Barcelona), monthly surface samples have been collected, and environmental variables such as temperature, salinity, dissolved inorganic nutrients (hereafter nutrients), and chlorophyll *a* (Chl *a*) have been routinely measured. Samples for the determination of *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrium*

diversity and their seasonal dynamics (by light microscopy and metabarcoding) were taken mainly at both stations during different periods of various years, depending on the approach used (see below).

The temperature profiles were obtained from conductivity temperature depth (CTD) casts. Salinity was measured from CTD casts in Blanes and from water samples analyzed with an AUTOSAL salinometer (OSIL, United Kingdom) in Barcelona. Nutrient samples were frozen prior to analysis. Soluble reactive phosphate, nitrate plus nitrite, nitrite, ammonium, and silicate concentrations were determined using the methods described in Grasshoff et al. (1999). Analyses were performed by continuous flow analysis (CFA) on a Bran+Luebbe (currently SEAL) autoanalyzer. Ammonium was measured by fluorometry. For Chl *a* analysis, 100 mL of water was filtered through Whatman GF/F fiber filters (25 μm diameter), which were subsequently frozen at -20°C until further processing. Before analysis, the filters were placed in 90% acetone for approximately 24 h in the dark, at 4°C . The fluorescence of the extract was measured with a Turner–Designs fluorometer (Yentsch & Menzel, 1963).

For the multivariate statistical analysis of the Blanes data, a precipitation index consisting of the accumulated precipitation (at the Malgrat de Mar meteorological station, about 6 km south of the Blanes sampling site) over the 7 days ending 2 days before each sampling date was used, since a significant positive relationship had been observed at this site between this index and the

Chl *a* concentration from several CHEMTAX groups, including diatoms (Nunes et al., 2018).

Monoclonal cultures

Strain isolation and maintenance

Monoclonal cultures were established using material obtained between 2015 and 2018, mainly from Blanes and Barcelona but also from surface samples collected at additional sites along the Catalan coast: Alfacs Bay ($40^{\circ}37' \text{ N}$, $0^{\circ}37' \text{ E}$), El Masnou Harbour ($41^{\circ}29' \text{ N}$, $2^{\circ}18' \text{ E}$), and the Olympic Harbour of Barcelona ($41^{\circ}23' \text{ N}$, $2^{\circ}12' \text{ E}$; Figure 1). Isolation was performed by pipetting a single cell or a single chain from the concentrated material on a 20- μm mesh, using glass capillaries and an inverted light microscope. The cultures were maintained at the Institut de Ciències del Mar in f/2+Si medium prepared with filtered (0.2 μm pore size) and autoclaved coastal seawater, under a light:dark cycle of 12:12 h, at $16\text{--}20^{\circ}\text{C}$, and illuminated with fluorescent tubes with a photon irradiance of about $100 \mu\text{m photons} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$.

Morphological analysis

Strains were examined (photographed and/or measured) with a Leica DMIRB inverted light

FIGURE 1 Location of the sampling stations (Alfacs Bay: $40^{\circ}37' \text{ N}$, $0^{\circ}37' \text{ E}$; Barcelona: $41^{\circ}23' \text{ N}$, $2^{\circ}13' \text{ E}$ (St. 1.4) and $41^{\circ}23' \text{ N}$, $2^{\circ}12' \text{ E}$ (Olympic Harbor); El Masnou Harbor: $41^{\circ}29' \text{ N}$, $2^{\circ}18' \text{ E}$; Blanes: $41^{\circ}40' \text{ N}$, $2^{\circ}48' \text{ E}$).

microscope equipped with a ProgRes C10plus JENOPTIK/Jena Laser Optik System digital camera. Different cell dimensions (apical, pervalvar, and, when possible, transapical axis) were measured from images, using the ProgResCapture Pro v.2.8.8 program. For each strain, at least 30 measurements of the apical and pervalvar axes (usually three cells per chain up to 50 cells) and as many as possible of the transapical axis (between two and 20, depending on the strain) were obtained. For scanning electron microscopy (SEM), several drops of culture were collected onto 3- μm polycarbonate filters, then washed with a few drops of bottled water and allowed to dry. Filters were mounted on stubs with colloidal silver, gold coated with a Q150R S sputter coated unit (Quorum Technologies, Ltd.), and examined at the Electron and Optical Microscopy Service of the Institut de Ciències del Mar (ICM-CSIC) under a HITACHI S-3500N scanning electron microscope (Hitachi High Technologies Corp., Tokyo, Japan), with an accelerating voltage of 5 kV.

DNA sequencing

Once the cultured strains reached high abundances, 10 mL were aliquoted into a plastic tube and harvested by centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 15 min. The resulting pellet was transferred to a 1.5-mL Eppendorf tube and centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 5 min. The supernatant was then removed and the pellet was stored at -80°C until processed. Different procedures were followed to obtain the nuclear rDNA gene fragments from the cultured strains. Full details on DNA extraction procedures, polymerase chain reaction (PCR) conditions, reagents, and primers used for each strain are in [Table S1](#).

Total genomic DNA was generally extracted from the pellets using the Qiagen Blood & Tissue commercial kit (Qiagen, The Netherlands), following the manufacturer's instructions for cultured cells. In some cases, nucleic acids were extracted with phenol and concentrated in an Amicon 100 (Millipore), as described in Massana et al. (1997). The amplification of complete SSU rDNA gene sequences was first attempted using primers EUK A–EUK B (Medlin et al., 1988). When not successful, the reverse primer 1209R (Giovannoni et al., 1988) or, alternatively, the primer pair EK82F–1520R (López-García et al., 2001) was used to obtain a partial SSU rDNA gene sequence. For partial LSU rDNA gene sequences, the primers D1R–D3B (Nunn et al., 1996; Scholin et al., 1994) were used. When not successful, the reverse primer D2C (Scholin et al., 1994) was employed instead. Unless otherwise specified in [Table S1](#), the PCR was carried out in 50 μL reactions containing 1 μL of genomic DNA, PCR buffer 1X with 1.5 mM of MgCl_2 , 0.2 mM of each type of dNTPs, 0.4 μM of each primer, and 1.25 U of Taq DNA polymerase (Qiagen, The Netherlands). Two

different PCR amplification programs were used, one for SSU rDNA gene fragments with an initial denaturation for 5 min at 94°C , 30 cycles of 45 s at 94°C , 60 s at 55°C , and 3 min at 72°C , followed by a final extension step for 10 min at 72°C and another for LSU rDNA gene fragments with an initial denaturation for 2 min at 94°C , 30 cycles of 20 s at 94°C , 30 s at 55°C , and 90 s at 72°C , followed by a final extension step for 5 min at 72°C . In some cases, the annealing temperature and the number of cycles were modified, as detailed in [Table S1](#). The PCR products were visualized under 1.2% agarose gel electrophoresis, and purification and sequencing were performed by an external service (Genoscreen, France), using both forward and reverse primers and a 3730XL DNA Sanger sequencer. For complete SSU rDNA gene sequences, internal primers 336F, 516R, 528F, and 1209F were also used. All fragments were merged, and consensus sequences were deposited in GenBank under the accession numbers PQ399702–PQ399716 for the SSU rDNA gene and PQ412650–PQ412679 for the LSU rDNA gene ([Table 2](#)).

Chaetoceros and *Bacteriastrium* seasonal dynamics

The seasonal dynamics of *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrium* were studied using light microscopy (LM) during two annual cycles (February 2017–2018 and February 2018–2019) in Blanes and Barcelona. For the in vivo identification and enumeration of *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrium* species in LM, 500 mL of the sample were concentrated by a mesh of 20 μm and then diluted in a known volume of filtered (0.2- μm pore size) seawater. Subsequently, an aliquot was settled into a 3-mL sedimentation chamber and counted by the Utermöhl (1958) technique. Additionally, phytoplankton samples were fixed with formol-hexamine to a final concentration of 0.4% (Thronsdén, 1978) in order to quantify organisms smaller than 20 μm , such as the solitary form of *C. tenuissimus*.

Seasonal dynamics were also studied by exploring the publicly available V4 SSU rDNA PRJEB23788 metabarcoding dataset from Blanes spanning the period from 2004 to 2013 (excluding 2011). Details on the metabarcoding sample processing can be located in Giner et al. (2019). Regarding the bioinformatic pipeline, raw Illumina paired-end reads from this dataset were trimmed with Cutadapt (Martin, 2011) and processed using the DADA2 pipeline (truncLen=240, 210; maxEE=6, 8; Callahan et al., 2016). Chimeric amplicon sequences variants (ASVs) were removed with the removeBimeraDenovo function, and sequences shorter than 300 bp were discarded. Taxonomic assignment was performed using Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST; Altschul et al., 1990) against the EukaryotesV4 database (Obiol et al., 2020). The

metabarcoding dataset comprised 91 samples corresponding to the nanoeukaryotic fraction (3–20 µm) and contained 5708 ASVs corresponding to microeukaryotic groups. Of these, 349 ASVs were assigned to diatoms (9.2% of the protistan reads); 84 of them belonged to Chaetocerotaceae (74 ASVs with a mean of relative abundance of 5.7% corresponded to *Chaetoceros* and 10 ASVs with a mean of relative abundance of 0.2% to *Bacteriastrium*). Only ASVs corresponding to Chaetocerotaceae were extracted from the complete dataset and analyzed in the present study. A heatmap was created with the heatmap.3 function (Griffith, 2015) using R (R Core Team, 2024). Bar plots were generated using the ggplot2 package (Wickham, 2016).

Phylogenetic analysis

The SSU and LSU rDNA gene sequences obtained from cultured strains in this study were assembled with sequences from GenBank representing the diversity of Chaetocerotaceae. Both datasets were aligned using the auto option in MAFFT v7 (Kato et al., 2019), and poorly aligned regions were trimmed using the automated 1 TrimAl option (Capella-Gutiérrez et al., 2009). For the SSU rDNA gene dataset, the previously selected ASVs were included in the alignment using the—add option of MAFFT v7. The best-fitting substitution model was selected for the alignments based on the Akaike information criterion (AIC) using jModelTest2 (Darriba et al., 2012).

The resulting SSU rDNA gene alignment comprised 202 sequences and 1729 positions. For the LSU rDNA gene, the alignment included 169 sequences and 725 positions. In both cases, maximum likelihood inference was computed by means of RAxML v8.0 (Stamatakis, 2014), using the GTRGAMMA model and 1000 runs with different starting trees. Bootstrap values were computed after 1000 pseudoreplicates. Amplicon sequence variants that showed greater than 99.5% identity with reference sequences were taxonomically assigned at the species level. Below this threshold, they were only assigned at the species level if they were included in a well-supported clade that included reference sequences. The remaining ASVs were only assigned at the genus level.

The final trees were visualized and annotated using iTOL v4 (Letunic & Bork, 2024). The list of sequences used to construct SSU and LSU rDNA gene phylogenetic trees, as well as the ASV information, is in Table S2.

Statistical analyses

A redundancy analysis (RDA) was performed on the Blanes dataset (integrating selected environmental

variables and species information obtained through metabarcoding) using the rda function from the VEGAN package (O'Hara et al., 2024). Species with a frequency of occurrence <20% were removed from the analysis. The dataset was normalized in R using the Phyloseq package (McMurdie & Holmes, 2013), based on the relative abundance of ASVs for each sample. All further analyses were conducted using R (R Core Team, 2024). Only species with scores greater than 0.05 on the first two RDA axes were labeled.

RESULTS

Chaetoceros and *Bacteriastrium* diversity, morphology and phylogeny

In this study, a total of 10 species of *Bacteriastrium* and 60 of *Chaetoceros* (most of them belonging to 15 different sections according to De Luca, Sarno, et al., 2019) including cryptic species were detected in Catalan coastal waters (Table 1). Among them, 39 species were identified from field material and monospecific cultures (Table 1). From the established cultures, both molecular (the LSU and often also the SSU rDNA gene) and ultramorphological (SEM) information was obtained for 23 species of *Chaetoceros* and one of *Bacteriastrium* (Table 2). The establishment of cultures and their subsequent morphological and molecular characterization allowed the detection of cryptic (*C. peruvianus* 1, *C. curvisetus* 1, *C. brevis* 1, *C. didymus* 2, *C. diversus* 1 and 2, *B. furcatum* 2) and two potentially new (*Chaetoceros* sp. ICMB68 and *Chaetoceros* sp. ICMB71) species (Figures 2 and 3) that were impossible to identify using LM alone.

The 84 ASVs assigned to Chaetocerotaceae corresponded to 59 different species (52 for *Chaetoceros* and seven for *Bacteriastrium*). This exploration allowed the detection of 31 additional species from metabarcoding data (Table 1). Among them, 12 *Chaetoceros* species and one *Bacteriastrium* species were only classified at the genus level because the sequences were not associated with taxonomically authenticated strain reference sequences in GenBank. All the cultured species were detected in the metabarcoding dataset, except *Chaetoceros* sp. ICMB68, *Chaetoceros* sp. ICMB71, *C. millipedarius*, and *C. diversus* 2. In addition, six uncultured species (*C. anastomosans*, *C. tortissimus*, *C. cf. tortissimus*, *C. vixvisibilis*, *B. jadrantum* and *B. elegans*) were observed in field samples and morphologically described by LM. Finally, four species of *Chaetoceros* (*C. atlanticus* var. *neapolitanus*, *C. dadayi*, *C. tetrastichon*, and *C. messanensis*) and three of *Bacteriastrium* (*B. biconicum*, *B. comosum*, and *B. elongatum*) were only identified from uncultured field samples, and we have provided their morphological descriptions by LM, except for *B. biconicum* (partially

TABLE 1 List of *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrum* species detected along this study by field samples observations (Field), after establishing and sequencing monoclonal cultures (Culture), and by exploring the available metabarcoding dataset (Metabar).

Taxa	Field	Culture	Metabar
Genus <i>Chaetoceros</i>			
Section <i>Anastomosantia</i>			
<i>C. anastomosans</i> (<i>C. anas</i>)	✓		✓
Section <i>Chaetoceros</i>			
<i>C. atlanticus</i> var. <i>neapolitanus</i>	✓		
<i>C. cf. convolutus</i>			✓
<i>C. dadayi</i>	✓		
<i>C. danicus</i> (<i>C. dani</i>)	✓	✓	✓
<i>C. peruvianus</i> 1 (<i>C. peru.1</i>)	✓	✓	✓
<i>C. rostratus</i> (<i>C. rost</i>)	✓	✓	✓
<i>C. tetrastichon</i>	✓		
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. A			✓
Section <i>Compressa</i>			
<i>C. contortus</i> cf. var. <i>contortus</i> (<i>C. cont.</i> cf. var. <i>cont</i>)	✓	✓	✓
<i>C. millipedarius</i>	✓	✓	
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. B (<i>Chaet.</i> sp.B)– <i>C. contortus</i> complex			✓
Section <i>Constricta</i>			
<i>C. constrictus</i>			✓
Section <i>Costata</i>			
<i>C. costatus</i> (<i>C. cost</i>)	✓	✓	✓
Section <i>Curviseta</i>			
<i>C. curvisetus</i> 1 (<i>C. curv.1</i>)	✓	✓	✓
<i>C. curvisetus</i> 2a/2b (<i>C. curvi.2a.2b</i>)			✓
<i>C. curvisetus</i> 3			✓
<i>C. galeatus</i>			✓
<i>C. pseudocurvisetus</i> (<i>C. pseu</i>)	✓	✓	✓
<i>C. tortissimus</i>	✓		✓
<i>C. cf. tortissimus</i>	✓		✓
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. ICMB71	✓	✓	
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. C– <i>C. curvisetus</i> complex			✓
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. D– <i>C. tortissimus</i> complex			✓
Section <i>Cylindrica</i>			

TABLE 1 (Continued)

Taxa	Field	Culture	Metabar
<i>C. lauderi</i> (<i>C. laud</i>)	✓	✓	✓
<i>C. teres</i>			✓
Section <i>Diadema</i>			
<i>C. diadema</i> 1 (<i>C. diad.1</i>)			✓
<i>C. seiracanthus</i>			✓
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. Clade Na13C1	✓	✓	✓
Section <i>Diadadia</i>			
<i>C. decipiens</i> (<i>C. deci</i>)	✓	✓	✓
<i>C. macroelegans</i>			✓
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. ICMB68	✓	✓	
Section <i>Laciniosa</i>			
<i>C. brevis</i> 1 (<i>C. brev.1</i>)	✓	✓	✓
<i>C. brevis</i> 2			✓
<i>C. brevis</i> 3 (<i>C. brev.3</i>)			✓
Section <i>Minima</i>			
<i>C. thronsenii</i>			✓
Section <i>Protuberantia</i>			
<i>C. didymus</i> 2	✓	✓	✓
<i>C. protuberans</i>	✓	✓	✓
Section <i>Simplicia</i>			
<i>C. tenuissimus</i> * (<i>C. tenu</i>)	✓	✓	✓
Section <i>Socialia</i>			
<i>C. socialis</i> (<i>C. soci</i>)	✓	✓	✓
Section <i>Stenocincta</i>			
<i>C. diversus</i> 1	✓	✓	✓
<i>C. diversus</i> 2 (<i>C. dive.2</i>)	✓	✓	
<i>C. willei</i>	✓	✓	✓
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. 3 (<i>Chaet.</i> sp.3)	✓	✓	✓
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. E– <i>C. affinis</i> complex			✓
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. F– <i>C. diversus</i> complex			✓
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. G– <i>C. diversus</i> complex			✓
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. H			✓
Not assigned to any section			
<i>C. messanensis</i>	✓		
<i>C. olympicus</i> *	✓	✓	✓
<i>C. vixvisibilis</i> / <i>C. cf. vixvisibilis</i> (<i>C. cf. vixv</i>)	✓		✓

TABLE 1 (Continued)

Taxa	Field	Culture	Metabar
<i>C. muellerii</i>			✓
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. Clade Na11C3 (<i>Chaet.</i> sp. Na11C3)			✓
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. Clade Va7D2 (<i>Chaet.</i> sp.Va7D2)			✓
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. SS628-11			✓
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. TG07-C28			✓
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. I			✓
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. J (<i>Chaet.</i> sp.J)			✓
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. K			✓
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. L			✓
Genus <i>Bacteriastrium</i>			
<i>B. biconicum</i>	✓		
<i>B. comosum</i>	✓		
<i>B. elegans</i>	✓		✓
<i>B. elongatum</i>	✓		
<i>B. furcatum</i> 2	✓	✓	✓
<i>B. hyalinum</i>	✓	✓	✓
<i>B. jadrinum</i> (<i>B. jadr</i>)	✓		✓
<i>B. mediterraneum</i>	✓	✓	✓
<i>B. parallelum</i> (<i>B. para</i>)			✓
<i>Bacteriastrium</i> sp.			✓
Total	39	26	59

Note: In parentheses, the abbreviated names of the species used in Figure 10. *In Arin et al. (2022).

isolated), for which ultramorphology was also observed by SEM.

The morphological description (and the corresponding photographic illustration) of most of the *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrium* species identified in this study as well as information on the morphometry (apical, perivalvar, and, when possible, transapical axis) of the cultured species, are reported in Data S1, Figures S1, and Table S3.

The tree resulting from the SSU rDNA gene phylogenetic inference showed the genus *Bacteriastrium* as a sister clade (100% bootstrap) to a clade comprising the genus *Chaetoceros* (79%; Figure 2). For the LSU rDNA gene phylogenetic tree, *Bacteriastrium* formed a clade with maximum statistical support within the *Chaetoceros* clade (Figure 3). The SSU and LSU rDNA gene sequences obtained for most of our strains matched between 99.5% and 100% with several GenBank sequences attributed to well-described species. Consequently, they were resolved within highly supported clades including known species. Likewise,

the morphological description of these strains generally coincided with the descriptions of the molecularly assigned species. In some cases, our SSU and LSU rDNA gene sequences belonged to undescribed species and were recovered within the *Chaetoceros* sp. clade Va7D2 and the *Chaetoceros* sp. clade Na13C1 or belonged to species with known cryptic diversity, such as *C. peruvianus*, *C. curvisetus*, or *C. didymus*. A new morphotype of *C. diversus* 2 (strain ICMB55) was observed in this study. The LSU rDNA gene sequence was identical to MG921665 (*C. diversus* 2 strain Na15C1) and MG921668 (*C. diversus* 2 strain Na56B2), whereas the SSU rDNA gene sequence showed 99.6% identity with MG972340 (*C. diversus* 2 strain Na56B2). The cells of this new strain were solitary or in pairs (no chain formation was observed), with the perivalvar axis longer than the apical one; a detailed description is in Data S1 and Figure S24.

Only in two *Chaetoceros* strains (ICMB71 and ICMB68) was the identity percentage with the closest sequence obtained from GenBank lower than 99.5%. In both cases, some morphological differences were observed with respect to their phylogenetically nearest species.

For strain ICMB71, the SSU rDNA gene sequence grouped independently of the other *Chaetoceros debilis* sequences (Figure 2), whereas the LSU rDNA gene sequence was included within the *C. debilis* sensu stricto clade (Figure 3). The closest matches to the SSU rDNA gene sequence (98.7% identity) were MG972248 and MG972250 (*C. cf. debilis* 2 strain Ch1A1 and Ch2B3, respectively), and the closest match to the LSU rDNA gene sequence (98.1%) was OK147722 (*C. debilis* strain HE492-61). Although organisms of our strain shared most of the general morphological characters of *C. debilis* (morphometry of the cells, presence of a single chloroplast per cell, hexagonal apertures, setae ultramorphology), they differed in the shape of the chain, the setae divergence from the apical plane, and the position of the rimoportula within the terminal valve. The LSU rDNA gene sequence of strain ICMB68 formed a clade with maximum support with KX065246 *C. mannaei* (99% identity) in the phylogenetic tree. Our strain shared many morphological characteristics with *C. mannaei* but presented differences in the cellular perivalvar/apical ratio (PA/AA), the mean pore size in setae, the density of poroids in the setae, and the rimoportula. The differences observed in both the molecular sequence and morphological features between strains ICMB71 and ICMB68 and their closest related species within each species complex might justify the consideration of these strains as new species (see the Discussion section for further explanations). A detailed description of these putative new species, designated as *Chaetoceros* sp. ICMB71 (the first) and *Chaetoceros* sp. ICMB68 (the second) is provided below. These provisional tags, based on the strain code of the first strain

TABLE 2 Strain code, isolation site, and date of the monoclonal cultures of *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrium* species obtained in this study. The GenBank accession numbers of the obtained molecular sequences are also listed.

Taxa	Strain code	Isolation site	Isolation date	LSU rDNA	SSU rDNA
Genus <i>Chaetoceros</i>					
Section <i>Chaetoceros</i>					
<i>C. danicus</i>	ICMB43	Barcelona	27-02-2015	PQ412672	PQ399710
	ICMB54	Barcelona	16-10-2015	PQ412675	
<i>C. peruvianus</i> 1	ICMB45	Blanes	13-01-2015	PQ412673	PQ399711
<i>C. rostratus</i>	ICMB67	Barcelona	01-12-2016	PQ412674	
Section <i>Compressa</i>					
<i>C. contortus</i> cf. var. <i>contortus</i>	ICMB56	Barcelona	16-10-2015	PQ412650	PQ399715
	ICMB66	Alfacs	10-05-2016	PQ412655	
<i>C. millipedarius</i>	ICMB50	Barcelona	20-02-2015	PQ412651	
Section <i>Costata</i>					
<i>C. costatus</i>	ICMB47	Blanes	13-01-2015	PQ412667	
	ICMB60	Barcelona	16-11-2015	PQ412653	PQ399716
	ICMB63	Barcelona	01-12-2016	PQ412668	
Section <i>Curviseta</i>					
<i>C. curvisetus</i> 1	ICMB41	Barcelona	27-02-2015	PQ412677	
<i>C. pseudocurvisetus</i>	ICMB57	El Masnou	25-10-2015	PQ412658	PQ399712
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. ICMB71	ICMB71	Blanes	16-03-2018	PQ412679	PQ399714
Section <i>Cylindrica</i>					
<i>C. lauderi</i>	ICMB52	Barcelona	28-04-2015	PQ412671	PQ399706
Section <i>Diadema</i>					
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. Clade Na13C1	ICMB51	Barcelona	20-02-2015	PQ412657	PQ399703
Section <i>Di cladia</i>					
<i>C. decipiens</i>	ICMB53	Barcelona	28-04-2015	PQ412652	
	ICMB58	Barcelona	16-11-2015	PQ412665	
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. ICMB68	ICMB68	Barcelona	01-12-2016	PQ412666	
Section <i>Laciniosa</i>					
<i>C. brevis</i> 1	ICMB42	Barcelona	27-02-2015	PQ412656	PQ399709
Section <i>Protuberantia</i>					
<i>C. didymus</i> 2	ICMB49	Barcelona	20-02-2015	PQ412654	PQ399707
<i>C. protuberans</i>	ICMB48	Barcelona	20-02-2015	PQ412676	PQ399708
Section <i>Simplicia</i>					
<i>C. tenuissimus</i> *	ICMB61	Barcelona	24-05-2016	MW561287	
	ICMB64	Barcelona	24-05-2016	MW561288	MW561277
	ICMB70	Barcelona	19-02-2018	MW561289	MW561278
Section <i>Socialia</i>					
<i>C. socialis</i>	ICMB40	Barcelona	27-02-2015	PQ412669	PQ399704
	ICMB44	Barcelona	27-02-2015	PQ412670	PQ399705
Section <i>Stenocincta</i>					
<i>C. diversus</i> 1	ICMB62	Alfacs	10-05-2016	PQ412660	
<i>C. diversus</i> 2	ICMB55	Barcelona	16-10-2015	PQ412661	PQ399702
<i>C. willei</i>	ICMB69	Barcelona	01-12-2016	PQ412659	
<i>Chaetoceros</i> sp. 3	ICMB46	Blanes	13-01-2015	PQ412664	
	ICMB59	Barcelona	16-11-2015	PQ412663	
	ICMB65	Blanes	07-06-2016	PQ412662	
Not assigned to any section					
<i>C. olympicus</i> *	ICMB72	Olympic	13-03-2018	MW561290	MW561279

TABLE 2 (Continued)

Taxa	Strain code	Isolation site	Isolation date	LSU rDNA	SSU rDNA
Genus <i>Bacteriastrium</i>					
<i>B. furcatum</i> 2	ICMB73	Barcelona	16-10-2015		
<i>B. hyalinum</i>	ICMB74	El Masnou	25-10-2015	PQ412678	PQ399713
<i>B. mediterraneum</i>	ICMB75	Barcelona	26-01-2017		

Note: Alfacs Bay: 40°37' N, 0°37' E, Barcelona: 41°23' N, 2°13' E (St. 1.4) and 41°23' N, 2°12' E (Olympic Harbor); El Masnou Harbor: 41°29' N, 2°18' E; Blanes: 41°40' N, 2°48' E. *In: Arin et al. (2022).

exhibiting that barcode, will allow future taxonomic assignment of all sequences and strains in databases and culture collections by replacing that provisional tag with the proper name.

Descriptions: Section *Curviseta* Ostenfeld, emended by Gran

Chaetoceros sp. ICMB71—Figure 4

Short to medium-sized chains are usually slightly twisted at one end of the chain (Figure 4a,b). Cells are square or rectangular in girdle view and elliptical in valve view (Figure 4a–c). Each cell contains a single, large chloroplast. The aperture is wide and hexagonal (Figure 4b,e). Setae emerge within the chain edge. Sibling setae cross each other after a long basal part at the chain margin (Figure 4b,e). Intercalary setae extend perpendicular to the chain axis (Figure 4a,b), or slightly toward one end of the chain (Figure 4d). Setae diverge equally from the apical plane at an angle of 45° (Brunel Group II, Figure 4c). Terminal setae are U-shaped, generally after an inflection point at their origin. The inflection point is variable in prominence, ranging from well-marked to very subtle (Figure 4b,d). Terminal valves bear a slit-shaped central rimoportula with an external tube (Figure 4f). Setae are circular in cross-section, bearing spirally arranged rows of poroids and spines (Figure 4g). Resting spores were not observed.

Section *Di cladia* (Ehrenberg) Gran, emended by Lebour

Chaetoceros sp. ICMB68—Figure 5

Small- to medium-sized, usually straight chains; occasionally, solitary cells are observed (Figure 5a,b). Cells are rectangular in girdle view and elliptical in valve view (Figure 5a–c). Each cell contains several small chloroplasts (Figure 5a,b). The aperture is wide and hexagonal (Figure 5a,d). Sibling setae cross immediately after the chain margin (basal part very short or absent; Figure 5d). Setae lie in the apical plane and diverge from the chain axis at an angle of 45–90° (Figure 5a). Terminal setae are either parallel to the chain axis or diverge at an angle of ca 45° (U- or V-shaped,

respectively; Figure 5a,b). The valve surface is concave with a slightly inflated central area (Figure 5c). The terminal valves bear an elliptical centric rimoportula without an external projection (Figure 5c). The mantle is low (Figure 5c,d). Setae are four-sided, each side bearing a row of oval poroids and regular spines along the borders (Figure 5e). Poroids in setae measure $0.49 \pm 0.09 \mu\text{m}$ in length, with a density of 14–20 poroids in $10 \mu\text{m}$. Resting spores were not observed.

Dynamics of environmental variables

The dynamics of abiotic variables (temperature, salinity, and inorganic nutrients) were similar in Barcelona (Figure 6a,c) and Blanes (Figure 6b,d). In both sites, there was a marked seasonality with higher surface temperatures in summer (maximum above 24°C in August) and lower in winter (around 13°C from January to March). The salinity in both zones ranged between 37.5 and 38.2 (Figure 6a,b). In general, the concentrations of inorganic nutrients were slightly higher in Barcelona than in Blanes. Minimum concentrations of phosphate, nitrate, and silicate were observed in summer (on average, 0.11, 0.39, and $0.75 \mu\text{M}$, respectively) while maximum values (on average, 0.14, 1.68, and $1.84 \mu\text{M}$, respectively) were observed in winter (Figure 6c,d).

Chlorophyll *a* peaked in March (end of winter-beginning of spring) with values around $1 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ and $2.5 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ in Blanes (Figure 6d) and Barcelona (Figure 6c), respectively. In both zones, the lowest values of Chl *a* were observed in summer (around $0.65 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ and $0.32 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ in Barcelona and Blanes, respectively).

Chaetoceros and *Bacteriastrium* seasonal dynamics

Light microscopy

The examination of live samples from Blanes and Barcelona coastal waters identified 31 *Chaetoceros* species and eight *Bacteriastrium* species (Table 1). Of the *Chaetoceros* species, only 23 were monitored

FIGURE 3 LSU rDNA gene phylogenetic tree including sequences of some *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrium* representatives of interest, and sequences obtained in this study from monospecific cultures (in bold). Sequences of *Porosira* sp., *Odontella sinensis*, *Thalassiosira weissflogii*, and *Dactyliosolen blavyanus* were used as outgroup. Black dots shown in nodes correspond to maximum statistical support (100% bootstrap value). To enhance visual clarity, the length of branches exceeding the scale of the figure was reduced to one fourth, being indicated by a break symbol (“//”). The different phylogenetic clades were labeled according to the sections proposed in De Luca, Sarno, et al. 2019. N.A. = species not assigned to any existing section. See Table S2 for the species name assignment used for each sequence.

but with an occurrence frequency equal or lower than 30% (data not shown). *Bacteriastrium jadrantum* presented a single peak exceeding 10,000 cells·L⁻¹ in early September 2018 in Barcelona (data not shown). The remaining *Bacteriastrium* species (Table 1) were detected at low (<3000 cells·L⁻¹) or very low population densities.

The dynamics of the dominant *Chaetoceros* species, as derived from LM observations, are represented

in Figure 7. During the studied period, *C. anastomosans* and *C. vixvisibilis* presented high abundances mainly in late spring and during summer, while *C. socialis* was abundant mainly in winter. Although maximum abundances of the *C. curvisetus* and the *C. lorenzianus* complexes were observed in winter and spring, respectively, high population densities of these species were also observed in other seasons (except in summer). High abundances of *C. tenuissimus* were

FIGURE 4 *Chaetoceros* sp. ICMB71. (a, b) Complete chains in girdle view; (c) cell in valve view; (d) chain in girdle view; (e) connection between two sibling valves of two intercalary cells; (f) terminal cell with a rimoportula; (g) detail of a seta. a–c: LM; d–g: SEM. Scale bars = 20 μm (a, b, c); 50 μm (d); 5 μm (e, f); 1 μm (g).

observed only in Barcelona during spring and early summer.

Metabarcoding dataset from Blanes

The Chaetocerotaceae representatives detected in the metabarcoding dataset from Blanes were dominated (average relative abundance >6% and occurrence frequency >30%) by four *Chaetoceros* species: *C. tenuissimus*, *C. socialis*, *C. cf. vixvisibilis*, and the *C. curvisetus* complex (as *C. curvisetus* 1 + *C. curvisetus* 2a/2b + *C. curvisetus* 3, although the first two species were predominant) and one species of *Bacteriastrom*: *B. jadrantum* (Figures 8 and 9). Other abundant and frequent species were *C. danicus* and *Chaetoceros* sp. clade Va7D2. A significant number of

species were detected with intermediate abundance and frequency (such as *C. contortus*, *C. costatus*, *C. anastomosans*, *C. decipiens*, *C. pseudocurvisetus*, *B. parallelum*, *B. hyalinum*, or *B. furcatum* 2), and a few were infrequent or rare, such as *C. seiracanthus*, *C. thronsdennii*, *C. brevis* 2, *C. olympicus*, *C. elegans*, *B. mediterraneum*, or *B. elegans* (Figure 8).

Among the dominant species, *Chaetoceros tenuissimus* was detected year round but showed higher relative abundances between March and October, representing >75% of Chaetocerotaceae abundance (Figures 8 and 9). Although *C. socialis* was detected throughout the year, it generally presented high relative abundances (>50%) during the late autumn and winter months and was less frequent in late summer and early autumn (Figures 8 and 9). The presence of *C. cf. vixvisibilis* was limited to a few months of the

FIGURE 5 *Chaetoceros* sp. ICMB68. (a) Complete chain in girdle view; (b) solitary cell in girdle view; (c) terminal cell in valve view showing central rimoportula; (d) connection between two sibling valves of two intercalary cells; (e) detail of a seta. a, b: LM; c–e: SEM. Scale bars = 20 μ m (a, b); 10 μ m (d); 5 μ m (c, e).

year (mainly in late spring and summer). No clear seasonal patterns were observed in representatives of the *C. curvisetus* complex, although their lowest relative abundances were observed in summer (Figures 8 and 9). Despite the seasonality observed in these dominant *Chaetoceros* species, their maximum relative abundances varied from year to year (Figure 9). Maximum relative abundances of *Bacteriastrium jadrantum* were observed at the beginning of summer, but the species did not present any clear seasonal pattern (Figure 8). Most of the other species were not detected in late summer and early autumn (such as *C. curvisetus* 3, *C. didymus* 2, *C. willey*, *C. peruvianus* 1, and the other *Bacteriastrium* species) or were detected sporadically (such as *C. anastomosans*, *C. decipiens*, and *C. lauderi*), whereas only a few (such as *Chaetoceros* sp. Clade Va7D2) were not detected in the winter and early spring months (Figure 8).

Chaetoceros and *Bacteriastrium* versus environmental variables

A multivariate RDA analysis was performed to explore explanatory environmental variables shaping the Chaetocerotaceae community. Most of the constrained variance in the RDA analysis was explained by the RDA1 axis (14.54%; Figure 10). Subsequent axes (RDA2–RDA5) explained progressively less variance (from

2.11% of RDA2 to 0.33% of RDA5). Axis RDA1, with a highly significant *p*-value (0.001), captured a prominent relationship between the response (species) and the explanatory variables (temperature, precipitation index, Chl *a*, and nitrate). The RDA1 axis clearly separated winter and summer samples with *Chaetoceros socialis* (winter) and *C. tenuissimus* (summer) as the organisms that best explained this variability.

DISCUSSION

Chaetoceros and *Bacteriastrium* diversity, morphology, and phylogeny

In this work, we were able to detect 60 species (including cryptic ones) of *Chaetoceros* and 10 of *Bacteriastrium* by combining morphological and molecular information obtained from field samples, cultures, and a metabarcoding dataset (Table 1). This was a comprehensive study of the Chaetocerotaceae family in Catalan coastal waters (northwest Mediterranean) and revealed a higher diversity than had been previously reported in LM studies of northwest Mediterranean coastal waters (Margalef, 1957, 1964, 1969; Margalef et al., 1957, 1959).

The different approaches used in this study were complementary for uncovering the diversity of *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrium*. Metabarcoding recovered the

FIGURE 6 Seasonal cycle (mean \pm SE) of (a, b) temperature and salinity and (c, d) inorganic nutrients (nitrate, silicate, and phosphate) and chlorophyll a, at surface waters of Blanes (a, c) and Barcelona (b, d) for the period 2004 to 2013.

highest diversity of Chaetocerotaceae, with a total of 59 species detected. Among these, 28 were also identified in field samples through LM. The most abundant taxa, including *Chaetoceros tenuissimus*, *C. socialis*, *C. vixibilis*, and *Bacteriastrium jadranum*, were consistently recovered by both methodologies. To our knowledge, species such as *C. constrictus*, *C. diadema*, *C. thronsdeni*, *C. muelleri*, and *B. parallelum*, which have only been recorded through the metabarcoding dataset, have not been reported before in northwest Mediterranean coastal waters. The failure to detect certain species by LM may be attributable to their rarity and low abundance (insufficient material for microscopic detection), the difficulty of reliable identification (weak or ambiguous morphological traits), or their small size—unless present in large numbers, species may be overlooked under LM. Metabarcoding analysis also revealed 13 taxa across different sections with ASV sequences that neither matched any reference barcode nor clustered within well-supported clades containing reference sequences. Several of these taxa were assigned

to species complexes, *Chaetoceros* sp. C within the *C. curvisetus* complex and *Chaetoceros* sp. E within the *C. affinis* complex (Figure 2; Table 1; Table S2), for example. Many of these species were rare and observed in low abundances, at least in the coastal waters of Blanes (Figure 8), which will likely make it difficult to obtain future morphological information about them.

The observation of field samples and the establishment of monoclonal cultures allowed the detection of additional species not revealed by metabarcoding, either because they were not present at the time of sampling or due to limitations caused by environmental DNA extraction efficiency, biased PCR amplification, or insufficient sequencing depth. Some species identified only by LM, such as *Chaetoceros dadayi*, *C. tetrastichon*, *Bacteriastrium biconicum*, *B. comosum*, and *B. elongatum*, lacked reference sequences in public repositories and could correspond to the ASVs assigned in this study as *Chaetoceros* sp. A (section *Chaetoceros*) and *Bacteriastrium* sp. (*Bacteriastrium* clade). These species exhibited morphological characteristics that were

TABLE 3 List of *Chaetoceros* species with both maximum abundance (Max.) > 10,000 cells · L⁻¹ and frequency (Freq.) > 30% in the Blanes and Barcelona datasets.

	Blanes		Barcelona	
	Max. (cells · L ⁻¹)	Freq. (%)	Max. (cells · L ⁻¹)	Freq. (%)
<i>C. anastomosans</i>	20,884	46	-	-
<i>C. curvisetus</i> complex	72,984	50	10,722	61
<i>C. lorenzianus</i> complex	10,736	75	26,400	65
<i>C. socialis</i>	27,450	42	33,856	43
<i>C. tenuissimus</i>	-	-	130,335	35
<i>C. vixvisibilis</i>	176,196	33	91,746	43

sufficiently distinctive to allow unambiguous identification under LM.

The metabarcoding dataset used in this study included only the nanoeukaryotic fraction (3–20 µm) of the entire <200 µm plankton community. This could have induced biases, because many of the *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrium* species detected here were larger than 20 µm in at least one of their dimensions (apical, transapical, or perivalvar axis; Table S3); it should also be noted that most species form long chains that increase their potential size. However, Piredda et al. (2018) and Cui et al. (2023), using metabarcoding, detected the same taxonomic composition across all size fractions of diatoms and *Chaetoceros* communities, respectively. As discussed in Piredda et al. (2018), there are several explanations for this observation, including mechanical or biological reasons, such as the physical rupture of the cell wall during filtration or differences in cell size and/or the formation of flagellate gametes during the life cycle of some species. The authors concluded that the metabarcoding analysis of the nanoplankton (3–20 µm) size fraction was the most realistic, as the relative contribution of the different diatom taxa was comparable to that obtained by LM.

The morphological features of most of the successfully characterized species agreed with their original description and the additional literature available. Likewise, the phylogenetic identity of cultured strains was highly congruent with their morphological identification. Only in the case of strain ICMB55, which showed >99.5% identity with sequences identified as *Chaetoceros diversus* 2, did we observe a particular morphotype that had not been assigned to this species so far. In strain ICMB55, all cells were solitary or in pairs, with U-shaped terminal setae (Data S1 and Figure S24). This solitary morphotype of *C. diversus* 2 differs from that reported in Moreno Ruiz et al. (1993), which had lower PA/AA ratios, but is consistent with that observed in natural samples from the Adriatic Sea by Bosak (2013), identified as *Chaetoceros* sp. “B” and proposed as a possible unicellular form of *C. diversus*.

Although the LSU rDNA gene sequence for strain ICMB71 (*Chaetoceros* sp. ICMB71) grouped within the *C. debilis* sensu stricto clade (Xu et al., 2020), its SSU

rDNA gene sequences formed an independent branch from the other *C. debilis* sequences (Figures 2 and 3). Strain ICMB71 differed from the general morphological characteristics of *C. debilis*. Chains of *C. debilis* are curved and, in valve view, setae are curved to one side of the apical axis (Xu et al., 2020), whereas in *Chaetoceros* sp. ICMB71 chains are generally straight or slightly twisted in one extreme of the chain, and setae diverge equally from the apical plane at an angle of 45° (Figure 4). Additionally, both species differ in the ultrastructure of the valve; in *C. debilis*, the rimoportula is eccentrically positioned (Kooistra et al., 2010; Xu et al., 2020), and in our strain, it is centrally located (Figure 4).

The LSU rDNA gene sequence of strain ICMB68 (*Chaetoceros* sp. ICMB68) formed a clade together with *C. mannaei* (Figure 3). Although our species shared most general morphological characteristics with *C. mannaei* (also common to other species of the *C. lorenzianus* complex; Li et al., 2017), it also presented important differences. Morphometrically, our strain showed a higher PA/AA ratio (5.17 vs. 1.65) with respect to *C. mannaei*, although this is a variable character because it depends on the stage in the life cycle of each species. Generally, diatom cells become smaller and elongated after successive mitotic divisions along the life cycle (Mann, 2011). Another notable ultrastructural difference was that in our strain, the rimoportula observed in terminal valves did not present an outward projection whereas in *C. mannaei* it had a long external tube (Figure 5). Furthermore, the mean size and density of poroids in setae were different, being smaller and denser in our strain than in *C. mannaei*. Li et al. (2017) observed that these last characters were useful for identification at the species level within the *C. lorenzianus* complex. Although more information is needed for a formal description, both *Chaetoceros* sp. ICMB71 and *Chaetoceros* sp. ICMB68, could be a new species within the *C. debilis* and *C. lorenzianus* complex clades, respectively.

The results on Chaetocerotaceae diversity were consistent with those obtained in nearby Mediterranean locations, like the Gulf of Naples, which resulted from morphological and molecular data to detect a

FIGURE 7 Temporal dynamic of dominant (>10,000 cells · L⁻¹ and frequency of occurrence >30%) *Chaetoceros* species observed by light microscopy in Blanes and Barcelona during two annual cycles (February 2017 to February 2019). (a) *C. anastomosans*, *C. lorenzianus* complex, *C. socialis*; (b) *C. curvisetus* complex, *C. tenuissimus*, *C. vixvisibilis*. Note the different scale in both plots.

substantial number of *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrium* taxa (Gaonkar et al., 2018, and references therein) or a time-series metabarcoding dataset (Gaonkar et al., 2020). Following these approaches, we detected the same *Bacteriastrium* species as in the Gulf of Naples (Gaonkar et al., 2020). The variety of *Chaetoceros* species detected in our work was also similar to that in the Gulf of Naples (Gaonkar et al., 2020), although some of the species reported in Naples were not observed in our dataset (such as *C. cinctus*, *C. circinalis*, *C. minimus*, *C. peruvianus* 2, and *C. roto sporus*, as well as several species not formally described, such as *Chaetoceros* sp. clade Na13C2, *Chaetoceros* sp. clade Na17B2, *Chaetoceros* sp. clade Na28A1, and *Chaetoceros* sp. GU823503). Conversely, we observed species such as *C. cf. convolutus*, *Chaetoceros* sp. TG07-C28, *C. galeatus*, *Chaetoceros* sp. ICMB68 and *Chaetoceros* sp. ICMB71 that were not detected in the Gulf of Naples, although the last three species may have been assigned as “Unknown” in the Naples metabarcoding dataset because some of them were described afterward.

Likewise, a haplotype corresponding to the environmental sequence FR874617 was shown in Gaonkar et al. (2020), which was identical to the sequence corresponding to *C. olympicus* (Arin et al., 2022). As in the Gulf of Naples, we observed cryptic diversity in *C. curvisetus* (*C. curvisetus* 1, *C. curvisetus* 2a/b, and *C. curvisetus* 3), *C. diversus* (*C. diversus* 1 and *C. diversus* 2), and *C. brevis* (*C. brevis* 1, *C. brevis* 2, and *C. brevis* 3). Most of the species that we also observed using LM of field material (such as *C. atlanticus* var. *neapolitanus*, *C. dadayi*, *C. tetrastichon*, *C. messanensis*, *B. biconicum*, and *B. elongatum*) had been similarly recorded by LM in the Gulf of Naples (Marino & Modigh, 1981).

Finally, the presence of species-specific inserts was detected in LSU and SSU rDNA gene sequences of strains belonging to specific sections such as *Stenocincta* and *Anastomantia* (Gaonkar et al., 2018). However, we could not observe any inserts in the sequences generated in this study, mainly because the sequences of those strains were not successfully obtained or they did not cover the region including the inserts.

FIGURE 8 Distribution pattern of 52 *Chaetoceros* and seven *Bacteriastrium* species over the 88 sampling dates (from 2004 to 2013, except 2011) in Blanes. The color scale represents the relative abundance of each species with respect to the total Chaetocerotaceae family. *C. curvisetus* complex = *C. curvisetus* 1 + *C. curvisetus* 2a/2b + *C. curvisetus* 3. See Table S2 for the species name assignment used for each sequence.

Seasonal dynamics of *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrium*

As reported in previous studies (Arin et al., 2013; Duarte et al., 1999; Guillén et al., 2018; Margalef, 1957), Barcelona and Blanes coastal waters present a strong seasonality, with temperatures varying from minima in winter (January to March) to maxima in August (Figure 6a,b). The phytoplankton biomass shows a peak in the winter-early spring period, in association with increasing daily irradiances, the stabilization of the water column, and the input of nutrients to the euphotic layers due to winter mixing. After a period of high stratification and low nutrient concentration in the upper water column, a second, less important peak occurs in autumn, when the disruption of the thermocline allows the return of nutrients to the surface waters (Figure 6c,d). Arin et al. (2013) and Nunes et al. (2018) observed by LM that *Chaetoceros* spp. were very abundant or dominant components of the two phytoplankton biomass peaks in both Barcelona and Blanes.

Most of the species of the Chaetocerotaceae family observed in this study varied across the seasons in recurrent ways throughout the studied period (Figure 8).

Both metabarcoding and microscopy revealed the dominance of four *Chaetoceros* species: *C. tenuissimus*, *C. socialis*, *C. vixvisibilis* (*C. cf. vixvisibilis*), and *C. curvisetus* sensu lato, which were the most abundant and frequent both in relative (metabarcoding) and absolute (microscopy) terms (Figures 7 and 8, Table 3), although with differences in their seasonal dynamics.

Chaetoceros socialis was more abundant in late autumn and winter, with low presence during summer (Figures 7 and 9). In fact, in Blanes, *C. socialis* was negatively associated with temperature and positively associated with nutrients (Figure 10). This species is common in temperate coastal waters (De Luca, Kooistra, et al., 2019) and is also dominant in other coastal areas of the Mediterranean, such as the Gulf of Naples (Gaonkar et al., 2020; Ribera d'Alcalà et al., 2004) and the Adriatic Sea (Bosak et al., 2016), where its maximum abundances have been observed during spring or autumn (Bosak et al., 2016; Ribera d'Alcalà et al., 2004 and references therein). The maximum abundances of *C. socialis* observed by LM in Barcelona and Blanes were in February and March, respectively, with water temperatures around 13°C (minimum temperature observed at both sites), suggesting

FIGURE 9 Seasonal patterns of ASVs assigned to *Chaetoceros* cf. *vixvibilis*, the *C. curvisetus* complex (*C. curvisetus* 1 + *C. curvisetus* 2a/b + *C. curvisetus* 3), *C. socialis*, and *C. tenuissimus* in Blanes from 2004 to 2013 (except 2010, 2011, and 2012).

that this temperature would be optimal or close to optimal for the growth of these organisms. This observation is consistent with those of Degerlund et al. (2012) and Huseby et al. (2012), who observed twice as fast growth of a *C. socialis* strain from the Tyrrhenian Sea (Mediterranean) at 13°C compared with at 2.5 and 8°C.

Chaetoceros tenuissimus had high abundances during spring and summer, although it was present year round (Figures 7 and 9). This species can be considered cosmopolitan (De Luca, Kooistra, et al.,) and is dominant in the Gulf of Naples (Gaonkar et al., 2020), with the highest abundances from the beginning of stratification throughout the summer (Ribera d'Alcalà et al., 2004). During the same period, this species is also present in the northeastern Adriatic Sea but at low abundance (Bosak et al., 2016). *Chaetoceros tenuissimus* was described as solitary (Meunier, 1913), but recently Arin et al. (2022) emended the original description and designated an epitype of this species including chain-forming forms as part of its life cycle. In Barcelona, Arin et al. (2022) reported maximum abundances of chain-forming and solitary forms in spring and early summer, respectively.

Chaetoceros vixvibilis was abundant in late spring and summer but was not present during the winter (Figures 7 and 9). This species is frequent in the Adriatic Sea and blooms during the spring-autumn period (Bosak et al., 2016; Hernández-Becerril et al., 2010; Viličić et al., 1995, 2009). In that area, blooms have been related to high seawater temperature, high phosphate (orthophosphate) concentrations (0.02–0.05 μM), and low salinity (lower than 33; Bosak et al., 2016). In the present study, phosphate concentrations in both Barcelona and Blanes exceeded 0.05 μM not only during the maximum abundances of *C. vixvibilis* (when minimum annual nutrient values were observed) but also throughout the year (Figure 6b). Likewise, salinity values were always higher than 37.6 (Figure 6a). In agreement with these observations, *C. cf. vixvibilis*, like *C. tenuissimus*, was associated in the RDA with high temperatures and low nutrient concentrations (Figure 10). In the metabarcoding data, this species was assigned as *C. cf. vixvibilis* (Gaonkar et al., 2018), since no resting spores (a distinctive character for identification) were observed in organisms associated with this sequence, and their setae were ornamented with

FIGURE 10 Redundancy analysis (RDA) ordination plot showing the relation of main *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrium* in the metabarcoding dataset samples and the environmental variables (Chl a, nitrate, silicate, and precipitation) in Blanes. Only species with a frequency of occurrence higher than 20% were considered. See Table 1 for full species names.

spines (which are absent in *C. vixvisibilis*). However, the period of maximum abundances of *C. cf. vixvisibilis* coincided with that of organisms matching the morphological characteristics of vegetative cells and resting spores of *C. vixvisibilis* (Bosak & Sarno, 2017; Hernández-Becerril et al., 2010), which were observed in field samples from the Blanes and Barcelona regions (Figure S29). Further studies are needed to clarify the identity of *C. vixvisibilis* and *C. cf. vixvisibilis* and to assess the co-occurrence of both, if they turn out to be different species.

The *Chaetoceros curvisetus* complex did not show a clear seasonality, although they were less frequent and abundant in summer (Figures 7 and 9). Among the three cryptic species of this complex detected by metabarcoding in this study (*C. curvisetus* 1 + *C. curvisetus* 2a/2b, + *C. curvisetus* 3), only *C. curvisetus* 1 and *C. curvisetus* 2a/2b were abundant and frequent; *C. curvisetus* 3 was detected only sporadically. All these cryptic species have also been detected in other areas of the Mediterranean Sea (De Luca et al., 2021).

Within the genus *Bacteriastrium*, *B. jadrantum* showed the highest relative (Figure 8) and absolute (data not shown) abundances, with maximum values detected in summer. This species has presented population peaks between September and November in the northeastern Adriatic Sea, also in association with high temperature and low nutrient concentrations (Bosak

et al., 2016 and reference therein). The sequence of *B. furcatum* obtained here through metabarcoding corresponded to *B. furcatum* 2, assigned to organisms of a strain from the Gulf of Naples (Gaonkar et al., 2018). Another sequence from a strain from the Adriatic Sea (Mediterranean Sea), attributed to *B. furcatum* in Bosak et al. (2015), was assigned as *B. furcatum* 1 in Gaonkar et al. (2018), since the sequences of both morphotypes were not resolved as sisters in the SSU and LSU gene trees, although organisms of both strains presented the same morphological characters. *Bacteriastrium furcatum* 1 peaked during late spring and summer in the Adriatic Sea (Bosak et al., 2016 and reference therein), while at our coast, *B. furcatum* 2 was not detected during this period by metabarcoding (Figure 8). However, low abundances (lower than $2000 \text{ cells} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) of *B. furcatum* (as identified by microscopy) were observed in both Blanes and Barcelona (data not shown). Most of the remaining *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrium* species were detected from late autumn to early summer. During mid-summer and early autumn, fewer species were recorded, including *C. vixvisibilis* and *C. tenuissimus*, already mentioned above, and others such as *Chaetoceros* sp. clade Va7D2 and *C. anastomosans* (Figure 8).

It should be noted here that the association of phytoplankton taxa with a particular environmental variable such as temperature does not need to be interpreted as the result of a direct effect of that variable but, rather, could be interpreted as a consequence of a succession of the phytoplankton populations associated with a multiparametric seasonal variability. Overall, this study supports the view that *Chaetoceros* shares the typical preference of diatoms for relatively turbulent and nutrient-rich conditions (Margalef, 1978), although the rich diversity of this genus also comprises species that thrive during the nutrient-poor summer and autumn seasons. Our study has provided a comprehensive view of the diversity and seasonal dynamics of *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrium* in the northwest Mediterranean coastal waters and emphasized the importance of combining morphological and molecular approaches to uncover the full extent of the diversity of this diatom family.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Laura Arin: Conceptualization (equal); formal analysis (equal); investigation (equal); writing – original draft (lead); writing – review and editing (equal). **Albert Reñé:** Conceptualization (equal); formal analysis (equal); funding acquisition (equal); investigation (equal); writing – original draft (supporting); writing – review and editing (equal). **Natàlia Timoneda:** Formal analysis (equal); investigation (equal); writing – review and editing (equal). **Rachele Gallisai:** Formal analysis (equal); investigation (equal); writing – review and

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

Data S1. Description of most of the *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrium* species included in this study.

Figures S1–S37. Photographic illustrations (LM and SEM) of *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrium* described in Supporting Data S1.

Table S1. Molecular procedures followed to amplify the SSU and LSU rDNA gene sequences of the cultured strains.

Table S2. List of sequences used to construct (a) SSU and LSU rDNA gene phylogenetic trees and (b) ASV information.

Table S3. Morphometric data of the different *Chaetoceros* and *Bacteriastrium* strains. Mean \pm SD, with minimum and maximum values in parentheses.

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